

Dye-sensitised Photo-oxidation of Thiosemicarbazide by Singlet Oxygen

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Kautsky¹ suggested that electronically excited metastable singlet oxygen molecules may be involved as 'an active oxygenation species' in dye-sensitised reactions. Singlet molecular oxygen as a reactive species for organic synthesis^{2,3} is generated by energy transfer from a photosensitiser with the singlet oxygen prepared either chemically¹ or by microwave discharge⁵. As a result, very intensive research on the chemistry, physics and biology of this intriguing intermediate species was stimulated. Extensive reviews unequivocally suggested the involvement of singlet oxygen in various systems⁶⁻⁹. Reviews of methods for the generation of singlet oxygen in the gas and in liquid phases as well as of its electronic states and spectroscopy have been published^{7,8,10}. Dye-sensitised photo-oxidation of alkane, alkene, aromatic hydrocarbons and nitrogen containing compounds has been reported¹¹. Compounds with thioamide group produce various photochemical decomposition products and the process is related to the presence of singlet oxygen^{12,13}. In polluted air, singlet oxygen is one of the photo-chemical intermediates. In order to throw some more light on this aspect a study of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide was under taken.

Results and Discussion

The photo-oxidation of thiosemicarbazide was carried out in presence of different sensitisers. The effect of triplet energy of various sensitisers on the yield of the photoproduct has been observed. As the triplet energy of the sensitiser was increased the yield of the photo-product decreased. All these triplet energies are sufficient for the formation of singlet oxygen $^1\text{O}_2$ (Δg) but Rose Bengal, eosin-Y, thionine and riboflavin have enough triplet energies for the transfer forming the singlet oxygen $^1\text{O}_2$ (Σg^+). The sigma

singlet oxygen is rapidly quenched in solution, so $^1\text{O}_2$ (Δg) is responsible for the oxidation⁹. The results are reported in Table 1¹⁴.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TRIPLET ENERGIES ON YIELD OF PHOTO-PRODUCT

Sensitiser = $3 \times 10^{-5} M$, Time of irradiation = 16 h

Sensitiser	Triplet energy kcal mol ⁻¹	Yield %
Rose Bengal	37.5-42.2	30
Eosin-Y	43.3-46.2	25
Methylene blue	34.0	20
Thionine	48.0	18
Riboflavin	57.8	12

The participation of singlet oxygen in the reaction was confirmed by the use of different singlet oxygen scavengers. In presence of singlet oxygen scavengers like nickel chloride, DABCO, β -carotene, cobalt chloride etc., no product was obtained.

The reaction products were characterised as semicarbazide, sulphur, sulphuric acid and sulphur dioxide. Sulphur, sulphur dioxide and sulphuric acid were detected by the usual methods¹³. Semicarbazide was confirmed by qualitative test. The sharp peak in IR spectra at 1620 cm^{-1} is resultant of overlapping of the absorption due to C=O stretching and NH_2 bending vibrations. The bands at 3390 , 3300 and 3180 cm^{-1} are due to N-H stretching vibrations. In mass spectral data weak parent ion peak at m/z 75, base peak at 44 and less intense peak at 59, 16 confirm the structure of the photoproduct. The control experiments were carried out as follows: (i) in presence of dye and air but no exposure to light, (ii) by passing air and light in the reaction solution but no dye was added and (iii) in presence of light and dye but no air was passed in the reaction solution. It was observed that in all the three cases semicarbazide was not obtained, thus confirming

the necessity of all the three components for this reaction.

In the proposed mechanism (Scheme 1) the singlet oxygen first attacks the thiosemicarbazide to give dioxetane (I) which undergoes decomposition¹⁵ to give semicarbazide and sulphur monoxide (II). The formation of dioxetane is in agreement with the earlier observation¹⁶. Sulphur monoxide is very short-lived species and it disproportionates to give sulphur dioxide (III) and sulphur¹⁷. The formation of sulphuric acid (V) may be due to the dissolution of SO₂ in water.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Thiosemicarbazide was purified by zone refining technique and thin crystals were grown from solution. The solution of dye and solvent water was used after filtration. All reaction solutions were irradiated in presence of air using filtered light (free from thermal-radiation) from a tungsten lamp.

The reactions were performed in presence of Rose Bengal solution ($3 \times 10^{-6} M$) containing $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ of thiosemicarbazide in water at room temperature. The air was continuously passed through the solution to stirred regularly. A tungsten lamp (Sylvania) was used for irradiation purpose maintaining a distance of 30 cm from the reaction vessel. A water filter was placed between the light source and the reaction vessel to cut off thermal (heat or ir) radiation.

After 10 h, some amorphous solid started to separate from the reaction solution. The resulting solid crystals of the product were recrystallised (m.p. 118^o).

The dye was removed from the filtrate by activated charcoal. The filtered solution was then treated with HCl to get the major product. The product was separated as semicarbazide hydrochloride (m.p. 177^o). The identity of the product was confirmed by physical, chemical and spectral analyses.

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